

RUSSIAN TEACHING METHODS FOR STUDENTS (USING THE EXAMPLE OF NATIONAL GROUPS)

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Abstract. *This article reveals the concept of the linguistic and didactic foundations of teaching Russian as a national language, examines linguistic phenomena in teaching Russian to national groups of students, analyzes teaching methods and the main difficulties and expediency of using the most effective linguistic and didactic teaching methods proposed in the framework of different methodological directions, in the modern practice of teaching Russian in national groups.*

Keywords: *russian as a national language, linguodidactic technique, communicative-oriented learning, methods, techniques, competencies.*

The term "linguodidactics" was introduced in the late 60s – early 70s of the XX century by academician N.M. Shansky, who developed the problems of language description for educational purposes. Linguistic and didactic foundations imply consideration of the language systems of foreign and native languages, which cannot but cause certain difficulties for the teacher. Linguist and academician L.V. Shcherba associated the linguistic and didactic aspect with theoretical linguistics, arguing that a "methodologist-linguist" engaged in teaching a foreign language "should not only know the language he teaches well, but also be a theoretical linguist in the full sense of the word".

The role of the method in teaching Russian as a foreign language (RCT) has always been a leading one. The Soviet psychologist B.V. Belyaev wrote in one of his works: "Since the teaching method should be understood as a set of basic methodological principles, the rejection of a particular teaching method, in fact, means the rejection of certain principles of learning. Anyone who denies the need for a basic teaching method strives to turn the methodology into an unscrupulous theory of learning, and the corresponding practice of this teaching into an unscrupulous activity." Methodological thought aimed at improving the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages has been developing for several centuries.

Modern teachers of a foreign language, including Russian as a foreign language, should strive to master the wealth of methodological possibilities accumulated during this time and creatively apply them in modern conditions using modern technical and information capabilities. Answering the question of what linguodidactics is (suggestive, a method of activating reserve capabilities, emotional-semantic, etc.). Natural and direct methods have enriched the methodology with methods of working on vocabulary (including non-translational methods of vocabulary semantics), and phonetics.

For the first time, phonetic, grammatical, and lexical material was minimized. Non-direct (audio-lingual and audiovisual) have armed us with an understanding of the importance of speech patterns as the minimum speech units to be learned, and training on them. They implemented the thesis that the process of language acquisition is a process of skill formation, which is ensured by repeated repetition. According to G. Palmer, ready-made samples are to be memorized and then used to construct sentences based on them by analogy. The main focus here was on sentence

construction models. M. West went down in the history of the technique, thanks to the "Read and say" technique, which helps not only connect reading and speaking, but also trains short-term memory.

The audiovisual method has enriched the methodology with techniques for working with filmstrips (frames of which can serve as supports for the development of speaking). Intensive methods have brought with them many game techniques: picture lotto, dominoes, various ball games, techniques for working with intonation and rhythm of the word: tapping, the technique of "intonation swing", etc. All statements are recorded on a dictaphone, and thus a text created by the students themselves is obtained. It is printed out, distributed to everyone the next day, and they continue to work with it.

The "Natural Approach" develops the ideas of the natural method about the primacy of methodology, science or art. One can answer that this is a synthesis of scientific principles that have crystallized through practice, and the creativity of a teacher who is able to skillfully, intelligently and flexibly combine different approaches and methodological techniques. Historically, conscious methods (consciously practical, grammatical translation, etc.) emerged first, followed by natural and direct methods (direct, audio-lingual, audiovisual), then communicative methods and intensive listening methods.

According to this method, the best way to present a large amount of material is storytelling (for example, small stories), where the same structures are repeated and new lexical units to be learned are found against their background. Speaking will not arise from scratch. It makes no sense to give tasks like "Create a dialogue." It needs to be approached methodically and competently. This is facilitated by the system of conditional speech exercises, which forms the skills necessary for speaking. Conditional speech exercises are exercises that form the automatism of using a form (structure), have a communicative task, but a given form of utterance

At the same time, the teacher gives the instruction to use a certain structure, which is aimed at by the cue-incentive. Pre-speech exercises are mostly done orally. This system consists of certain types of exercises: imitative, substitution, transformative, to expand the speech pattern, reproductive. Only after that, when the lexical and grammatical skills of using the appropriate vocabulary and grammar are formed, you can proceed to speech exercises. At the same time, speech exercises should also be communicatively justified and involve interrelated learning of all types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading and writing. Communicatively justified means reflecting the real situations of communication and the real communicative behavior of its participants.

The Interviewers and Interviewees game (a press conference by one of the group members who can be assigned a role, the rest of the group members play the role of newspaper correspondents and ask various questions). Working on listening as the flip side of oral speech, it is necessary to develop all the mechanisms necessary for successful listening: short-term memory, concentration of attention, the mechanism of anticipation (probabilistic forecasting), folding and spreading of structures. For example, the following techniques can be used to develop short-term memory: "Snowball", "Read and say", writing words from memory, dictation with a single presentation of a sentence, free dictation, etc.; to develop the mechanism of anticipation (and at the same time reaction, which is also necessary for successful communication), you can use a ball, for example, with the task: "finish the sentence" "give me a phrase," etc. Even reading can become an assistant in speaking if you use the "Read and say" technique (read a sentence to yourself, then

raise your head and repeat it aloud, which also develops short-term memory), different types of retelling of what you read. read it. As exercises in text reproduction with the inclusion of new grammatical and lexical phenomena, for example, different forms of retelling can be proposed. Retelling is an extremely useful and effective exercise in reproduction, allowing you to reproduce the text you have seen or heard, it is a good "bridge" for moving to the actual speaking, to the production of speech. However, teachers often turn this exercise into a boring activity that does not arouse any interest among students and reduces its effectiveness to virtually zero.

The same can be done for paragraphs for larger semantic pieces of text. This technique helps to develop writing skills. A good exercise to prepare for retelling is to reconstruct the text using reference words, which are best used as verbs, since they convey the dynamics of the narrative text, as well as the reasoning text. When studying verbs of movement in a foreign audience, dictation in drawings followed by verbal reproduction is very effective. The essence of this exercise is that the teacher reads a text full of movement verbs with different prefixes, and the students make schematic drawings, according to which they then have to reproduce the text orally or in writing. A teacher of Russian as a foreign language should remember that he is like an artist who, mixing different colors, creates with strokes a unique artistic canvas – a person who knows a foreign language culture.

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